

Complexes of Rare Earths and Their Biocidal Properties

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Mixed-ligand complexes of the type MAB (where M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III}; A = TAR (tartaric acid)/MAL (malic acid); B = HQ (8-hydroxyquinoline) have been investigated potentiometrically. During the formation of above species ligand B coordinates to the initially formed 1 : 1, MA complexes in the second step. Ir spectra and elemental analyses of the isolated complexes have also been carried out in support of the potentiometric results. The resulting complexes and involved ligands have been studied to find out the percentage inhibition (at 200 ppm) on some selected fungi and bacteria.

A survey of the literature revealed that the formation of binary and ternary complexes of rare earths with TAR and MAL¹⁻⁴ and HQ^{5,6} as one of the ligands have been extensively studied. The information about the role of metal complexes in biological systems, their concentration and their presence in different equilibrium is of immense importance. Gershon *et al.*⁷⁻⁸ reported that the activity of metal chelate is considerably increased as compared to that of the free metal and the ligands alone on their complexation. Similar observations have also been noted on 8-HQ⁹ and by Cu^{II} complexes¹⁰ with hydroxy acids and heterocyclic compounds and also on rare earth complexes¹¹. In continuation to our previous studies^{12,13} it was, therefore, thought worthwhile to investigate some more ternary complexes of rare earths involving HQ and hydroxy acids potentiometrically.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of the AR, BDH or Fluka grade. The standard solutions of metal nitrates¹⁴, KNO₃, KOH, and potassium hydrogen phthalate¹⁴, hydroxy acids¹⁵ and HQ.H⁺ were prepared as described earlier.

Instrument and methods : pH-metric titrations were carried out with a Philips PR 9405M pH meter with a calomel and standard glass electrode assembly, standardised for pH 4 at 25 ± 1°. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer IR 4250 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Similar curves were obtained for all the mixed systems M^{III}-TAR/MAL-HQ (where M^{III} = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III}). For the sake of brevity only the curves for the systems La^{III}-TAR/MAL-HQ have been discussed.

Curve b (Figs. 1 and 2) ascribes the titration of HQ mono-hydrochloride. A well defined inflection at m=1 indicates titration of loosely attached proton of the HQ.H⁺. A single well defined inflection at m=2 on the curve c (Figs. 1 and 2) shows the simultaneous titration of both the carboxylic protons of the acids¹⁵ (TAR and MAL), respectively.

Binary systems : Curve d (Figs. 1 and 2) represents the potentiometric titration of 1 : 1, La^{III}-HQ binary mixture. An almost overlapping nature of this curve to the curve b upto m~1 probably indicates the titration of the ligand hydrochloride alone in acidic medium. The occurrence of a yellow solid at m>1 and the appearance of a sharp inflection at m=2 attributes to the formation of 1 : 3, La^{III}-HQ complex⁵ which is further supported by the appearance of one more inflection at m~4 probably due to the precipitation of the remaining metal as metal hydroxide and the colour of the solid phase changing from yellow to whitish yellow.

Curve e (Figs. 1 and 2) depicts the titration of 1 : 1, La^{III}-TAR/MAL binary systems, respectively. The lowering in initial pH and an inflection at m=2 may be correlated to the formation of 1 : 1, binary complexes in both the cases. One more inflection at m=3 in case of La^{III}-MAL can be attributed to the deprotonation of the initially formed protonated species resulting in the formation of a neutral complex¹⁶ as evidenced by the formation of a solid phase at m > 2. The other inflection at m~3.5 in the system 1 : 1 La^{III}-TAR (Fig. 1) may, however, be ascribed to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1 : 1 complex into 1 : 2, La^{III}-TAR soluble species¹⁷ with the simultaneous precipitation of the remaining metal as its hydroxide at higher pH.

Ternary systems : The initial superimposable nature of the curve f (Fig. 1) for 1 : 1 : 1, La^{III}-

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Fig. 1. Curve b-HQ.H⁺; c-TAR; d=1:1, La^{III}-HQ; e=1:1, La^{III}-TAR; f=1:1:1, La^{III}-TAR-HQ; T-Theoretical composite curve; and →=appearance of ppt.

Fig. 2. Curve b-HQ.H⁺; c-MAL; d=1:1, La^{III}-HQ; e=1:1, La^{III}-MAL; f=1:1:1, La^{III}-MAL-HQ; T-Theoretical composite curve; and →=appearance of ppt.

TAR-HQ mixed system to the curve e (Fig. 1) and an inflection at m=2 may be attributed to the formation of 1:1, La^{III}-TAR binary complex. The lowering in the upper buffer region, an appearance of a solid (at m>2) and its partial dissolution with a sharp inflection at m~5 at higher pH (~8) may probably be attributed to the simultaneous coordination of the secondary ligand HQ and one of the OH groups of TAR to the initially formed 1:1, La^{III}-TAR binary complex resulting in the formation of 1:1:1, La^{III}-TAR-HQ ternary species as follows:

The initial superimposable nature of the curve f to the curve e (Fig. 2) and an inflection at m=2 shows the priority of complexation of MAL with metal ion resulting in the formation of 1:1, La^{III}-MAL complex. The further lowering in pH and an inflection at m~4 may probably be correlated to the addition of HQ.H⁺ to the initially formed 1:1, La^{III}-MAL complex. One more inflection at m~5 can be ascribed to the titration of hydroxyl proton of the MAL at high pH as evidenced in the binary complex forming 1:1:1, soluble species as observed by an almost dissolution of the solid phase.

The formation of above ternary complexes is further supported by (i) non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve T^{2a} with the curve f in the region of mixed ligand complex formation, (ii) a partial dissolution of solid phase at higher pH in both the cases, and (iii) ir spectral studies and the analyses of N, C, H and metal (M) of the isolated complexes (Table 1)

Complex	Analysis: Found/(Calcd.)			
	M	N	C	H
La ^{III} -HQ-TAR-H ₂ O	30.33 (30.85)	2.95 (3.11)	33.85 (34.65)	2.28 (2.44)
La ^{III} -HQ-MAL-H ₂ O	30.78 (31.34)	3.05 (3.15)	34.00 (35.20)	2.40 (2.48)

Ir spectra: A comparative study of the ir spectra of the complexes with those of the involved ligands shows the appearance of some new bands as well as

TABLE 2—BIOCIDAL ACTIVITY

Fungi*/Bacteria**	Substance	Concn. ppm	Inhibition %
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	HQ/TAR/MAL	200/500/500	88/20/25
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	HQ/TAR/MAL	200/500/500	90/10/10
<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	HQ/TA/MAL	200/500/500	80/10/20
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	LaIII-TAR/MAL-HQ	200/200	100/100
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	LaIII-TAR/MAL-HQ	200/200	100/100
<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	LaIII-TAR/MAL-HQ	200/200	100/100
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	LaIII-TAR/MAL-HQ	200	78/90
<i>Streptococcus</i>	"	200	90/100

* Antifungal activity at 28° after 96 h.

** Antibacterial activity after 48 h.

lowering in the stretching frequencies of active groups in the ir spectra of the complex. The appearance of new bands at 3400 and 1600 cm^{-1} indicate the antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching and H—OH bending¹⁹, respectively due to coordinated water molecules. A sharp band at

1575 cm^{-1} corresponds to O—C=O stretching of the involved acid and clearly indicates the chelation through its COOH group. The coordination of the ligands to the metal ions through N and O is further supported by the appearance of bands at 485 (M—N)²⁰ and 435 and 360 cm^{-1} (M—O)²⁰. Further, the presence of strong bands in the region 1170-1120 cm^{-1} probably indicate the presence of coordinated oxine²¹ in the complexes.

Biological studies : Observations on the biocidal activity of the substances are reported in Table 2.

The observation of Table 2 reveals that the complexes have been found to be more active as compared to the free metal and ligands involved. The increased activity of the complex is probably due to their combined activity effect of both the ligands in the metal chelate, due to their more liposoluble nature on being coordinated with the metal ion forming a stable metal chelate or due to a comparatively faster diffusion of the metal complex as a whole through the cells of the fungi which is in accordance with our earlier observations^{19, 18, 22}.

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